

A STANDARDIZED ANALYSIS OF REGULARITY OF DEPRESSION AMONG THE ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To study the regularity of depression among undergraduate engineering students of private engineering colleges in Karachi, Pakistan. **Study design:** Cross-sectional study. **Setting:** The study was conducted at different private engineering colleges, Karachi in May 2019 till October 2019. **Material and Methods:** A cross-sectional study was organized on randomly selected private engineering colleges of Karachi. Sample size of 181 was calculated by using software SPSS version 22. A close ended, self-administered, modified form of standardized questionnaire was used which was comprised of 2 parts. First part included collection of socio-demographic data, second part had questions for the assessment of depression. Hamilton Depression Scale (HAM-D) was utilized in scoring the depression level in the

study subjects. **Results:** Among 181 engineering students, 31(17.1%) were normal. 61(33.7%) presented with mild depression, 37 (20.4%) had moderate depression, 24 (13.3%) had severe and 28 (15.5%) were found to be severely depressed. **Conclusion:** In the present study, level of depression was higher in engineering students. It is advised in future that depression reducing intervention needs to be encouraged in professional program.

KEYWORDS: Depression, Hamilton Depression Scale (HAM-D), Medical students, Student mental health.

INTRODUCTION

According to World Health Organization (WHO), depression is the main cause of dysfunction worldwide. It can affect any individual regardless of race, age, ethnicity or sex but is more prevalent in the young generation, specifically among the students. Depression is a mood disorder that involves a tenacious feeling of dejection, misery, loss of interest or feeling 'blue'. Depression is a serious medical condition that can negatively impact all aspects of one's life including, how they feel, think, and act.^[1] Many factors can influence and trigger depression. Its symptoms vary among each individual and include stomachache, headache, diarrhea, somnolence, insomnia, amnesia, eating disorders and many more. There are many causes of depression but the most common is the academic pressure put forth by the institutes and universities.^[2,3] The mental health of university students is considered the most crucial among the public health area. Physiological and psychological stress among engineering students is common as compared to other professional courses. Engineering students are the future of our society; they embody it, so their mental wellbeing is vital not only for them, but also for society, as they are the ones who contribute the most to society.^[4,5]

The psychological problems like stress, anxiety, depression among engineering students are increasing every year. High workload and syllabus, exams burden is a major cause of promoting depression among engineering students.^[6] That's why drugs abuse and suicide rate seems to be high in engineering students. Depression has been known to be more prevalent in developing countries as compared to developed countries, this is mostly attributed to the socioeconomic, political instability and the greater rates for unemployment found. As students enter professional and undergraduate education, the dramatically significant rise in pressures and expectations can lead to feelings of anxiety further progressing to depression.^[7] Depression has been reported to have a great impact on the students' performance both personally and academically. Depression during university years can lead to lower academic performance further leading to fewer employment opportunities, deterioration of personal relationships and lower self-esteem.^[8,9]

In light of spiraling educational stress and a broadening in diagnosed mental illnesses among the students, this article offers the all-embracing of depression found among the engineering students of Pakistan. Many university students experience some symptoms of depression

during the course of their studies which lead to their low grade or failure not only in their academic section of life but also in their other aspects of life.^[10]

This study aims to identify the impact of mood disorder i.e depression among a sample of students in the engineering field of undergraduate students. The results indicated that the burden of studies had some impact on the depressive symptoms of the university students of engineering section.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A cross-sectional study was conducted on engineering students of randomly selected engineering colleges of Karachi in May 2019 till October 2019. The sample size was 181 of engineering students. By taking written informed consent and conserving anonymousness, the tool use for data collection is a close-ended, self-administered, a modified form of standardized questionnaire.

The other part of the study which have objective variables which will be used to determine severity of common depressive symptoms of engineering students of Karachi. This objective will be assessed by Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D). The original 1960 version contain 17 items (HDRS-17). For 17 items version, a score of 0-7 is considered to be normal, score of 20 or higher indicate moderate, severe or very severe depression.

The inclusion criteria for this survey include undergraduate engineering students of any gender of Karachi, between 18-30 years of age. The exclusion criteria for this survey includes students having any chronic life threatening disease, students having any psychological disorder, students having family history of psychological disorders, students who refuse to give written consent.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data was fed into the computer using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software program version 22. Data will be presented using descriptive statistic in the form of frequencies and percentage for qualitative variables.

RESULTS

Depression among engineering students is common as compared to other professional programs. Engineering students spend most of their time in projects/ research work/ field work etc. and get less time for any activity which helps to relief their stress. The sample size

was 181 of engineering students. This objective will be assessed by Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D). In engineering 102 were of age ranged between 17-20 years, 79 between 21-24 years. The mean age for engineering was 20.40 ± 1.523 . Out of total 181 engineering students 107 were male and 74 females. Male students were dominated in engineering colleges. In engineering all 181 students were single. In engineering 60, 37, 38 and 46 students were of 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th professional year respectively. 181 engineering students had semester system curriculum (Table 1).

Among 181 engineering students, 31 (17.1%) were normal, 61 (33.7%) presented with mild depression, 37 (20.4%) had moderate depression, 24 (13.3%) had severe and 28 (15.5%) were found to be severely depressed which were highly statistical significant (Table 2).

Table 1: Variables of age, gender, religion, marital status, professional year & system curriculum.

Variable		Engineering students(n=181)	P value
Age (in Years) Means $\pm$ SD		20.40 $\pm$ 1.523	.000
Gender	Male	107	.000
	Female	74	
Religion	Muslim	181	0.044
	Non-Muslim	0	
Marital Status	Single	181	0.317
	Married	0	
Professional Year	1st year	60	.000
	2nd Year	37	
	3rd year	38	
	4th year	46	
	5th year	0	
System curriculum	Semester	181	.000
	Yearly	0	

$p < 0.005$ significant difference by t-test

Table 2: Level of depression among undergraduate engineering students (Based on Hamilton Depression Scale).

Depression Scale	Engineering Students		P-value
	Count	Percentage	
Normal	31	17.1%	.000
Mild	61	33.7%	
Moderate	37	20.4%	
Severe	24	13.3%	
Very Severe	28	15.5%	
TOTAL	181	100.0%	

$p < 0.005$ significant difference by t-test

DISCUSSION

Depression leads to significant problems in the performing of one's activities of daily living (ADLs) further causing problems in interpersonal and professional relationships along with decreased interest in daily routine activities.^[1] It can present with a range of symptoms from sleep disturbances, lack of attention, anxiety, a general lack of interest in normal life activities, eating disorders, and suicidal risk. It can persist for long periods of time, often lasting for years if left untreated. It is estimated that around 480 million people suffer from depression worldwide, half of which suffer from anxiety as well. Depression has been reported as one of the most common health problem for engineering students as well.^[11,12]

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines health as “a state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity”. Talking about mental health is still regarded a stigma, and millions are suffering silently from mental illness without any help or support.^[13]

Depression is a psychiatric disorder characterized by loss of interest and pleasure (anhedonia), decreased energy, feeling guilty, low self-esteem, disturbed sleep and poor concentration are a major global health problem. It is the 11th leading cause of global disease burden, a noted cause of disability with an estimated global point prevalence of 4.7%.^[14] Several studies have described that the mental health of university going students are poorer as compared to their counterparts in the general population with depression being on the top of it. University students transition from adolescents to adulthood and experience social and physical changes and cognitive incongruity in emotional, behavioral, sexual, economic, academic and social areas.^[15] This may also affect peer and family relationships, their academic performance and physical mental health. Moreover, individuals may fall a prey to substance abuse habits to overcome depression and in severe conditions an individual ends up committing suicide. Depression adversely affects interpersonal, social and occupational aspects of student's life which is also known as multi-dimensional disorder.^[16]

Among young college going students with professional education appear to be exposed to more mental stress as compared to others, this may be attributed to factors like tough competition for a limited number of seats, high academic workload, increase duration of courses meeting the expectations of teachers and parents, vast curriculum, future study concerns, poor grades in exams, low self-esteem, future employment and achieving a stable a financial future.^[17]

This study aims to evaluate the prevalence of depression in engineering students in Pakistan. This study was taken on to evaluate the prevalence of symptoms of depression among engineering students and the results revealed an alarming upshot of 82.9%. In India 36% of engineering students were found to be suffering from depression. As stated by the past studies, regulated in this area, the mutilating effects of depression on human brain includes brain shrinkage and inflammation, oxygen restriction and many more. Not only do they cause interruption and disruption in the academic section of life but may also have some other consequences like diabetes, cardiovascular disease, Alzheimer's, stroke, cancer and more. Studies done at two large universities in Ankara, Turkey, revealed that the regularity of depression among medical and engineering students was found to be 13.8% and 16.4% respectively. Relatively, the regularity of depression among engineering students was much higher, with approximately 73.8% of students witnessing depression.

Results of this study reveal that there is a negative relationship amongst depression and educational achievement of engineering students, which indicates that, the higher the depression amidst students, the lower their achievement's level. In another study conducted in Karachi, Pakistan 2020 by Siddiqui *et al.*, the ratio of depression in engineering students was increased.^[1] These results are also supported by our study indicating that depression among first year, second year and final year engineering students was increased.

CONCLUSION

We concluded from this study that depression was high in engineering students. The understanding among engineering students about depression was better. Universities should put forth coping skills programs for students witnessing depression and programs related to prevention of depression should also be suggested.

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